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Research Article

KNOWLEDGE ATTITUDE AND PRACTICES OF OBESITY AND WEIGHT MANAGEMENT AMONG NURSES

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Abstract:

Introduction: The pandemic of overweight and obesity in developed and developing countries presents a challenge to public health and requires medical intervention, modifications of individual behavior, and environmental changes.

Objectives: The main objective of the study is to analyse the knowledge attitude and practices of obesity and weight management among nurses. **Material and methods:** This cross-sectional study was conducted in Punjab Institute of Cardiology, Lahore during 2019 to 2020. We assessed the following characteristics: billing sector (in the controlled billing sector, the fee per consultation is set by the Health Insurance Administration. **Results:** Most GPs regarded obesity as a disease and agreed that their role includes weight problem management, but 57.5% felt that they do not manage it effectively. Approximately 30% considered overweight and obese patients lazier and more self-indulgent than normal weight people, and 57.2% were rather pessimistic about these patients' ability to lose weight. GPs rated food intake as a significantly more important risk factor for obesity than stress, hormonal problems, or unemployment.

Conclusion: It is concluded that nurses felt that management of weight problems was one of their responsibilities.

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INTRODUCTION:

The pandemic of overweight and obesity in developed and developing countries presents a challenge to public health and requires medical intervention, modifications of individual behaviour, and environmental changes (1). Epidemiological studies in France, Spain, and Italy have shown this disease striking the Mediterranean area, where food habits have long seemed to protect against cardiovascular risks (2).

General practitioners (GPs) have a significant role to play in preventing and diagnosing weight problems and in providing initial counseling. They are, after all, the health professionals consulted most often, and most patients believe that their GPs could and wish they would help them to lose weight (3). Nonetheless, GPs do not manage overweight and obesity satisfactorily, as they themselves recognize: they identify only about one-half of their overweight or obese patients and advise only one-third of these patients to lose weight.

GPs' attitudes toward and practices in the management of weight problems have been studied in various English-speaking countries, but we are aware of very few published studies from Mediterranean countries. Obesity has become a global epidemic. In 2016, 39% of women and 39% of men aged 18 and over were overweight. Surgical treatment of obesity and metabolic disorders increases rapidly in China, but it is still a new discipline even to health professionals and there is low awareness among nurses. There are not many professional bariatric case managers; thus, bariatric patients are mainly cared for by nurses. As an important member of the multidisciplinary team, the knowledge and attitudes of the nurses provide crucial health care to the patients and support to surgeons. However, the role of nurses is often undermined/neglected in health education, promotion counselling, and postoperative follow-up.

Objectives

The main objective of the study is to analyse the knowledge attitude and practices of obesity and weight management among nurses.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This cross-sectional study was conducted in Punjab Institute of Cardiology, Lahore during 2019 to 2020. We assessed the following characteristics: billing sector (in the controlled billing sector, the fee per consultation is set by the Health Insurance Administration; in the noncontrolled billing sector, GPs freely set their own fees according to market pressure and patient income), solo/group practice, subscription to medical journals, guidelines use, involvement in a health network (coordinated group of several health professionals organized to improve health care in a specific medical field), and postgraduate medical degrees. We also asked about their height and weight (for calculating their BMI), personal experience of dieting, behavior related to food intake, physical activity, and tobacco consumption. Eleven items allowed us to examine GPs' perception of weight problems, involvement in their management, and perception of their training, effectiveness, and professional gratification in this field. Three items assessed their opinions about overweight and obese patients on a four-point Likert scale.

The data was collected and analysed using SPSS version 19. All the values were expressed in mean and standard deviation.

RESULTS:

Most GPs regarded obesity as a disease and agreed that their role includes weight problem management, but 57.5% felt that they do not manage it effectively. Approximately 30% considered overweight and obese patients lazier and more self-indulgent than normal weight people, and 57.2% were rather pessimistic about these patients' ability to lose weight. GPs rated food intake as a significantly more important risk factor for obesity than stress, hormonal problems, or unemployment. They also rated the medical consequences of obesity as more important than its psychological and social consequences.

Table 01: Nurses attitude towards obesity

Statement	n	Strongly disagree	agree	Strongly agree	Rather agree
Obesity is a disease	595	2.5	7.2	33.4	56.8
Normal weight is important for health	599	0.7	0.2	16.9	82.3
For overweight and obese patients even small weight loss can produce health benefits	596	0.0	0.8	21.5	77.7
Most overweight patients should be treated for weight loss	598	0.8	5.9	47.5	45.8
Only obese patients should be treated for weight loss	595	40.2	39.8	14.6	5.4
Obesity management is necessary in the long term	598	0.2	0.3	15.9	83.6
GPs' role is to refer overweight and obese patients to other professionals rather than attempt to treat them themselves	594	31.0	48.0	17.5	3.5
GPs should be models and maintain normal weight	595	7.7	8.7	53.1	30.4
I feel well prepared to manage overweight and obese patients	596	5.9	26.5	44.6	23.0
Treating overweight and obese patients is professionally gratifying	595	7.6	23.9	48.4	20.2
Obese people are lazier and more self-indulgent than normal weight people	597	27.3	41.9	26.1	4.7
Overweight people are lazier and more self-indulgent than normal weight people	594	25.9	45.5	24.9	3.7
Only a small percentage of overweight and obese people can lose weight and maintain this loss	597	11.9	30.8	48.2	9.0

DISCUSSION:

Obesity has become a global epidemic. Surgical treatment of obesity and metabolic disorders in China is increasing rapidly, but it is still a new discipline even to health professionals. Even physicians and other

health-related professionals may not know much about bariatric surgery. In addition, older nurses were more likely to be overweight or obese compared to younger nurses. This finding is consistent those reported in the literature [13]. Nurses working in administrative

departments had higher incidence (3.2%) of obesity than that in clinical departments. A foreign study found that 36.2% of nurses were obese who worked in administration and management.

Chinese nurses have a strong sense of losing weight, but few actually do it. Our data showed that 59.4% of nurses believe that they need to lose weight, but only 38.7% of nurses have a habit of regular exercise. On the one hand, it may be due to a lack of motivation; on the other hand, it may be that they possess insufficient time for exercise due to large workloads. A study has also showed that some nurses may not follow recommended guidelines for nutrition and exercise which may be related to gender and age.

CONCLUSION:

It is concluded that nurses felt that management of weight problems was one of their responsibilities. Although their diagnostic practices require improvement, most of their reported practices follow the guidelines relatively closely.

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